

USING THE GAME METHOD IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: *In recent years, the emphasis on the study and teaching of foreign languages has increased significantly. This is done to make foreign language lessons, especially English, more interesting, that is, using a variety of innovative methods, techniques and interactive games that challenge a wide variety of students. Using these games throughout the lesson further enhances students' interest in learning the subject. This article describes techniques for learning English through games.*

Key words: *foreign language, interactive games, technical means, didactic games, role-playing style, game grammar, taboo words (forbidden words), Pictionary game).*

Today, due to the importance of foreign language learning, languages are taught not only in higher education institutions, schools, but also in preschool educational institutions. Attracting students to the lesson can become a somewhat complex task if special methods and interesting methods are not used in the lessons. If lessons are conducted in an engaging manner, avoiding traditional methods, this not only ensures the quality of the lesson, but also prevents boredom and attracts passive students to participate in the lesson.

There are a number of interesting games in the process of teaching English. It should be noted that when teaching children a language, it is necessary to avoid games in which all students participate equally and learn new things from the lesson (for example, new dictionaries can be memorized, if this process is repeated every day, the student's vocabulary will rise to a high level). It is inappropriate for students to start the lesson with grammatical concepts, especially for younger schoolchildren. As a result, interest in the lesson may be lost.

Even the greeting process with them should be started in an unconventional way, for example, the method of starting the lesson with some kind of greeting English song (primarily a motivational method for elementary school students) as soon as the teacher enters is an effective method. If the lesson continues in this way, students will not lose their attention to each task during the lesson. They even look forward to English lessons. Of course, the teacher must organize all this, and it is the teacher's responsibility. Therefore, to make learning a foreign language interesting, it is possible to list some types of games.

Role-playing games can be used to enhance the effectiveness of English lessons. The advantage of this game is that it is played based on the situation. This game is not only useful for the study of science, but also helps to develop intellectual abilities. In this game, the topics are chosen, and the children organize dialogues. For example, the conversation of a passenger in the process of stopping a taxi, or conversations in clothing stores - all this is said and shown in English. It is precisely in this game that we can apply the tactics of

working with a group, that is, dividing students into groups and dividing them into different topics. In this case, competition also arises. Competition is a criterion for growth. When a group that has successfully completed the assignment is encouraged, the aspiration of the remaining students also increases. In addition, it is advisable to use didactic games to effectively conduct English lessons.

OBJECT is a game that serves to enhance students' vocabulary. We know that the most important direction in the study of foreign language subjects is the memorization of new vocabulary. Taking into account the characteristics of the students, each student memorizes the dictionary in their own way. We believe that memorizing new words through games is suitable for everyone and makes this process easier. In the game we mentioned above, 15 items in the classroom are placed on the table during the lesson, and the students come and look at these items. The items are covered, and then the students must write down what they have seen, in English, on the board for a certain period of time. The winner is the student who writes the most words correctly. To ensure the quality of this game, I can say that in order to attract students who are not involved in this situation, it is advisable to give them the task of composing one sentence for the names of these items, and this also prevents indifference.

Pictionary - for most English language teachers and learners, this game is familiar, that is, a word game with its own name and a picture is drawn on it. In this game, you can use a plain board or magnetic board to draw. The students in the class are divided into two groups and a table is drawn on both sides of the board for each group. Teams' scores are recorded in these tables. Word names are written on the desk and rotated in reverse. From each group, students take turns choosing one of the hidden words and drawing it on the board. The team that scores first will be awarded a point. This game also sharpens the minds of students. We can also say that the use of images is a tactic that quickly engages students, especially if it is created by the students themselves.

The game **Taboo Words (Forbidden Words)** is an interesting game that helps students use synonymous words and their definitions. The use of synonyms ensures fluency of speech and beauty of conversation. Especially in English, it is necessary to avoid mistakes related to the use of words, as many words with the same meaning in English are used according to the content of the sentence. It is this game that helps us be cautious in this regard. In this case, groups are organized, meaning that students sit opposite each other. Each team selects one person from their team to sit in the chair opposite them. The teacher stands behind the students and holds a word written on a large piece of paper. Students sitting in a chair should not be able to see this word. There will be some time for the member of the team sitting in the chair to say what the teacher is holding.

The goal of a **tennis game** is to increase the speed of students. This game is similar to a chain game and takes place within the chosen theme. In this case, he must say a new word to the last letter of the said word, for example, if the title of the topic is "Animals," he begins with the word "Tiger" without deviating from the topic, while the second participant

continues with "rabbit." And so the game proceeds. A student who stops during the game and fails to respond for 5 minutes is dismissed from the game and resumed with the remaining students. Playing the game with the class, that is, with the majority, is very interesting and engaging. You can also play this game by changing the theme. At the same time, in the process of organizing games, connecting them with various technical means also serves to increase interest. Because in today's rapidly developing world, all young people, adolescents, and adults are not indifferent to modern technologies. Therefore, it is possible to achieve effective results by organizing interesting scientific games on computers.

Indeed, when teaching, grammatical concepts are also taught, as this is indicated in the teachers' lesson plans. However, there is also a game to make this process easier and more fun. For example, subject words (parts of speech). They need to learn parts of speech well and be able to distinguish them from each other. Students can be given the task of writing only words related to the noun group while listening to music in English, and then another group of words can be given to the student. Thus, the topic is strengthened, and this method can be applied in the process of transitioning to other topics. It can also be organized as a cultural entertainment for students.

When using games, we can change them depending on the children's knowledge and age, that is, make them easier or more complex. The goal of these games is to strengthen students' memory, enhance their intellectual potential, speed, wit, easy memorization of new words, and most importantly, to organize a meaningful lesson. Today, although the educational process is mainly conducted in a traditional way, the organization of continuous foreign language learning at all levels of the education system, as well as the improvement of teachers' qualifications and the provision of modern teaching materials, requires further improvement. It is advisable for the younger generation, through the introduction of advanced teaching methods with modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies, to become specialists in the languages they are studying, and consequently, they should be able to speak these languages fluently. After all, all this is for the great future of our youth, for the prosperity of our country.

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